

MULTISCALE AND MULTILEVEL ANALYSIS OF COMPOSITE STRUCTURES WITH BOLTED JOINTS

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SUMMARY

The present paper deals with a computational strategy to model the strength of bolted joints in composite structures. The rupture of the global structure is determined thanks a two-level level strategy. At the local scale, a detailed Finite Element model of the single-bolt joint, taking into account delamination, is used.

Keywords: bolted joints, bearing failure, progressive damage, non-local calculation methods, multilevel strategy

INTRODUCTION

Due to their high specific strength and stiffness, Carbon Fibre-Reinforced Plastics (CFRP) are increasingly used in aeronautical applications. These applications usually require the use of mechanical joints in order to transfer loads between composite laminates and other composite or metallic parts. Therefore, ability to joint elements efficiently is necessary for a full exploitation of high performance fibre-reinforced plastics. Nevertheless, ensuring the load transfers between composite and other composite or metallic parts remains problematic. Since the use of bonded joints is often prohibited by the industrial imperatives of reproducibility and maintenance, mechanically fastened joints - such as bolted or riveted joints - are preferentially used. However, composite components are considerably weakened by the drilling of holes, mostly because of the resulting high stress concentrations. For instance, the strength of a bolted joint could be, in some cases, 50% lower as compared with a plane plate. The mechanical joint is often a limiting factor for the overall performance of the structure that severely handicaps the replacement of the existing light alloy structures by composite solutions. It is thus an absolute necessity to predict the behaviour and the strength of bolted joints.

Two kinds of approaches are proposed in the literature to attain this goal. The first one, could be called "brittle criterion approach". The main idea consists in using, as a post-processing of an elastic finite element calculation, a failure criterion using stresses calculated on characteristic curves associated to each mode of rupture [12]. However, the characteristic lengths involved in these methods are a function of the stacking sequence, of the geometry of the joints etc... This is the reason why some authors have proposed a second kind of approach that could be called "progressive damage model". The main idea of this approach consists in taking into account the effect of the most significant physical phenomena experimentally observed : non-linear behaviour of the matrix, matrix rupture, fibre rupture and delamination. Lot of authors have focused on the matrix and fibre ruptures (see [3,4]) since these two modes of ruptures are responsible of the final failure in shear (matrix failure), in tensile (fibre failure in tension) and bearing (fibre failure in compression). The delamination, which has an

important effect on the global behaviour and the final rupture, is most of the time studied using rupture criterion and its effect is taken into account by few authors [5]. Moreover, using complex softening models lead to numerical problems [6] that are not always addressed. The definition of the final failure, which is another very important point, is generally characterized by the divergence of the FE calculation.

This article aims at proposing a strategy adapted to complex fastened composite joints. The first section of this paper is thus devoted to the presentation of a 3D progressive failure approach. A cohesive zone model is used in order to describe the delamination and its effect. A comparison with experimental results is also proposed. The second section is devoted to the application of this approach to an industrial case thanks to the use of virtual testing. Finally, a conclusion and a discussion are proposed in the last section.

MULTISCALE ANALYSIS OF SINGLE-BOLT COMPOSITE JOINTS

Presentation of the multiscale model to describe the behaviour and the rupture of bolted joints

The proposed approach is based on the physical phenomena observed in composite joints (matrix crack, fibre failure in tension and in compression, delamination). The ply level has been considered as the pertinent scale to describe these phenomena. The behaviour of the unidirectional ply is based on a damage thermo-viscoelastic model and is written as follows :

$$\sigma = \tilde{\mathbf{C}} : (\varepsilon - \varepsilon^{\text{ve}} - \varepsilon^{\text{th}})$$

where σ is the stress, $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ is the elastic stiffness tensor, ε is the total strain, ε^{th} is the thermal strain and ε^{ve} the viscoelastic strain (modelled using a viscoelastic spectral model [7]).

The mesoscopic failure criterion is based on physical principles and makes a distinction between the fibre failure (FF, criterion f_1) and the matrix failure (IFF, criterion f_2) modes.

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} f_1 = \left(\frac{\langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_+}{X_t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \varepsilon_1 \rangle_-}{X_c} \right)^2 \\ f_2 = \left(\frac{\langle \varepsilon_2 \rangle_+}{Y_t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \varepsilon_2 \rangle_-}{Y_c} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\varepsilon_6}{S_c} \right)^2 \end{array} \right. \text{ with } \begin{cases} \langle X \rangle_+ = X, \text{ if } X \geq 0, \langle X \rangle_+ = 0, \text{ if } X < 0 \\ \langle X \rangle_- = X, \text{ if } X \leq 0, \langle X \rangle_- = 0, \text{ if } X > 0 \end{cases}$$

The effect of a crack on the mechanical properties of a ply is described thanks to a damage model. After the first failure of a ply in the laminate (failure criterion value is higher than 1), the effective elastic compliance $\tilde{\mathbf{S}}$ of the failed ply is increased

$$\tilde{\mathbf{S}} = \mathbf{S}^0 + d_1 \mathbf{H}_1 + d_2 \mathbf{H}_2 \quad \begin{cases} \text{FF} & d_1 = \alpha \langle \sqrt{f_1} - 1 \rangle_+ \\ \text{IFF} & d_2 = \beta \langle \sqrt{f_2} - 1 \rangle_+ \end{cases} \quad d_i \geq 0$$

where \mathbf{S}^0 is the initial elastic compliance, \mathbf{H}_1 and \mathbf{H}_2 are fourth order tensors that respectively represent the effect of fiber failure (damage variable d_1) and inter-fibre

failure (damage variable d_1). The identification of this model necessitates only five tests performed on a UD ply and one test on a laminate to identify the parameter β .

In order to avoid numerical problems of damage localization due to the use of softening degradation rules, a delayed damage approach is employed [8]. The identification of the parameter of this approach does not necessitate any test and could be seen as a numerical parameter.

Cohesive zone elements are used to simulate the interface between the plies. The behaviour of these interfaces is elastic with softening damage rules in normal tension and shear; moreover, friction is taken into account in shear. The mechanical behavior of the interface is described by the relation between the normal and tangential relative displacements (U_n , U_t) of the nodes, and their respective normal and tangential tractions (T_n , T_t). The damage evolution is taken into account by the damage variable λ which combines the tension and the shear damages as follows [9]:

$$\lambda = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\langle U_n \rangle_+}{\delta_n}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{U_t}{\delta_t}\right)^2}$$

The non-linear relations between (U_n , U_t) and (T_n , T_t) have the form:

$$\begin{cases} T_n = \frac{U_n}{\delta_n} F(\lambda) \\ T_t = \alpha \frac{U_t}{\delta_t} F(\lambda) \end{cases}$$

and $F(\lambda)$ is chosen as $F(\lambda) = \frac{27}{4} \sigma_{\max} (1-\lambda)^2$ for $0 \leq \lambda \leq 1$, where σ_{\max} and $\alpha \sigma_{\max}$ are respectively the maximum values of T_n and T_t in pure modes. The damage parameter λ varies continuously from 0 (locally bonded case) to 1 (locally debonded case). The complete separation between two corresponding nodes occurs for $\lambda=1$ ($F(\lambda)=0$) so that δ_n and δ_t are the maximum values of the relative displacements U_n and U_t in pure normal and pure shear modes respectively. The interfacial parameters have been identified thanks to classical fracture mechanics tests.

Finite Element multi-model strategy

A mesh convergence study has been performed in [10]. This study has shown that it is possible to establish some rules which permit to insure that the mesh is fine enough. Moreover, in order to model the in-ply damage and the delamination, it is necessary to describe the laminate thanks (at least) one element by ply and cohesive zone elements between each plies. Finally, the number of degree of freedom could become tremendous when the number of plies increase. In order to overcome these difficulties a multi-model strategy is used.

The main idea consists in reducing the complexity of the models (FE mesh and material behavior) as a function of the distance of the hole (see Figure 1. The parts located far from the zone of interest are modeled using only one element in the thickness and the homogenized orthotropic elastic behavior of the laminate. The transition with the zone of interest is performed using multilayer element and the elastic behavior for each ply.

Finally, in the zone of interest, at least one element in the thickness of a ply is used and a cohesive zone element is introduced between the plies. In this zone, the behaviour of the ply is described using the proposed model. In order to decrease the number of dof, the cohesive zone elements are only introduced near the singularities. The junction between each parts of the mesh is insured thanks to displacement conditions between the nodes (Multiple Point Constraints).

Figure 1 : Multi-model strategy

The main difficulties of this approach lie in the choice of the size of the zone of interest. Indeed, if the damage (ply rupture or delamination) reaches the border of the interest zone the modeling has no more physical sense. However, a progressive meshing strategy is under development to overcome this difficulty. It is worth to mention that in the present study, a great attention has been paid to this problem.

Comparison with experimental results

The present section is devoted to the comparison with experimental results. A progressive comparison is proposed. The first comparisons are performed on T300/914 laminates [10]. First of all, test cases on open hole and filled hole plates are investigated. The next step concerns the modeling of bearing tests with different diameter of hole. Finally, tests on double lap joints subjected to tensile loads and bypass and bearing loadings are investigated. The last comparison concerns the same kind of tests but performed on another material (T700/M21 material).

The parameters of the model have been identified thanks to experimental tests performed on UD ply provided in [10]. Moreover, it is well known that the coefficient of friction between the insert and the composite is a very sensitive parameter. As suggested in [11], this coefficient has been chosen equal to 0.05.

Open-hole and filled-hole tests on T300/914 laminate.

The experimental and numerical results are presented in Table 1 and in figures 1 and 2. All these results have been obtained on a $[90_2/0_2/90_2/0_2]_s$ laminate. The thickness is close

to 2mm, the diameter of the hole (d) is equal to 6 mm and the ration width (w) over diameter is equal to 3. Each test has been repeated twice. The first ply failure loading has been measured thanks to acoustic emission.

Table 1 : Comparison between experimental and numerical results for open-hole and filled-hole test specimens

Type of specimen	First ply failure (N)			Final failure (N)		
	Model	Test (mean value)	Error	Model	Test (mean value)	Error
Open-hole	6339	7200	-13%	16361	14735	10%
Filled-hole	5590	5835	-4%	16272	14360	11.7%

Figure 2 : Comparison between experimental and numerical results for open-hole tests

Figure 3 : Pattern of damage (a) delamination, (b) fibre ruptures and (c) matrix ruptures at the end of the test

The results obtained by the model are in quite good agreement with the experimental results as well as at a global point of view (loading curve, final failure) and as a local one (first ply failure). It could be noted that, due to the use of a delayed damage approach to overcome localization, the final failure is slightly overestimate.

Bearing tests on T300/914 laminate.

The experimental and numerical results are presented in Table 2. The stacking sequence and the geometry are the same than in the previous paragraph. Different diameters of hole have been investigated. For each diameter the ratio w/d is equal to 3.

The comparison shows that the model permits to reproduce in a quite good manner the evolution of the bearing strength as a function of the diameter of the hole.

Table 2 : Comparison between experimental and numerical results for bearing tests

d (mm)	First ply failure (MPa)			Rupture en matage (MPa)		
	Model	Test (mean value)	Error	Model	Tests (mean value)	Error
6.40	200	199	0.25%	216	214	1%
8.15	277	278	-0.54%	288	315	-9%
10.20	285	280	1.75%	291	324	-11%
12.15	262	312	-18%	265	263	0.75%

Bypass and bearing loading tests on double lap joint T300/914 laminate .

The experimental geometry is presented in Table 3. First, a bearing load equal to 5200 N is applied to the test specimen. A tensile load is then applied up to the rupture. The first test is performed on a 32 plies specimen with the $[(45/0/-45/90)_4]_s$ stacking sequence. The second test is performed on the same kind of specimen only disoriented of 22.5° .

Table 3 : Comparison between experimental and numerical results for bypass and bearing tests

Test	D (mm)	w (mm)	e (mm)	L (mm)	Failure load (N)		
					Model	Test	Error
1	6,35	35	50	100	30463	39113	-22%
2	6,35	35	50	100	27922	30887	-10%

The experimental failure occurs by traction. The modelings confirm this scenario and show that there is no bearing crack initiated prior to the rupture. Figure 4 shows the fibre rupture located at 90° of the load axis and the delamination pattern.

The numerical results are in quite good agreement with the experimental ones. It seems that the model underestimates the failure load. It could be explained by the lack of knowledge (i) in the longitudinal compressive strength and (ii) in the kinetic of this mode of failure.

Figure 4 : In the left: interfacial delamination between ply at -45° and 0° . In the right: fibre failure in 0° plies.

Bearing test and open-hole tests on T700/M21 laminates

In order to validate the present model on an other material (T700/M21 with a ply thickness equal to 0.26mm), tensile tests on open-hole laminate and a bearing test have been realized [12]. The open-hole tensile tests have been performed on a 32 plies laminate ($[0/-45/90_2/45/90_2/-45/90/45/90_2/-45/0/45/90]_s$). The width of the plate is equal to 45.7mm and three different diameters of hole have been investigated (see Table 4). The bearing test has been performed on a $[90/45/0_2/-45/0_2/45/0/-45/0_2/45/90/-45/0]_s$ test specimen (the geometry is given by $w=49.6\text{mm}$, $d=9.52\text{mm}$ and $e=23.8\text{mm}$, see table 3).

Table 4 : Comparison between experimental and numerical results of open-hole tests and bearing test on T700/M21 laminates

d (mm)	Open hole specimens			Bearing specimens		
	Test (kN)	Model (kN)	Error	Test (kN)	Model (kN)	Error
7,94	97	112	13%	65	54	-16%
9,52	89	98	9%			
12,70	80	90	11%			

The numerical results are in quite good agreement with the experimental ones. As for the T300/914 laminates, it seems that the model (i) overestimates the experimental results for the open hole tests specimens and (ii) underestimates the experimental results for bearing tests.

MULTILEVEL ANALYSIS OF COMPLEX INDUSTRIAL COMPOSITE JUNCTIONS

Industrial approach for complex industrial composite joints

In an industrial point of view, a two-level strategy is used in order to describe the rupture of complex bolted joints in composite structure involving several hundred of fixations (see fig. 2, left of the figure). Firstly, global calculation is performed in order to evaluate the behavior of the whole junction in its environment. Because of the geometrical complexity of the structure, coarse meshes and simple material behavior are used. The joints are replaced by springs with an equivalent stiffness identified according

a semi-empirical formula provided. Secondly, strength of the critical fixations is evaluated at local-level calculations.

The loads issued from the global calculation are injected as input data for the local reanalysis of the critical fasteners, using semi-empirical models (see Figure 5). It is supposed that there is no bolt-hole clearance. By respecting some classical design guidelines for the geometry of the joint and the choice of the stacking sequence, shear-out failure mode can be easily avoided. Therefore the critical failure mode taken into account in the model is a combination of tensile and bearing failure modes. Failure occurs when the following criterion is reached :

$$K_t \cdot (\sigma_t^n + K_m \cdot \sigma_m) \geq \sigma_r \quad (3)$$

Where: σ_t^n is the average tensile stress in the net cross-section,
 σ_m is the average bearing stress,
 σ_r is the admissible stress,
 K_t and K_m are respectively the hole coefficient and the bearing coefficient.

K_t and K_m are empirical coefficients whose identification requires many experiments. These coefficients depend on the material, the stacking sequence, the nature of the bypass loads (tension or compression), the diameter D of the fasteners and the loading direction. Moreover, the hole coefficient also depends on the pitch w , and whether it is large enough for the holes to be considered independent or not ($w < 5D$).

Figure 5 : Multilevel strategy to study the failure of a complex joint structure.

In our point of view, the industrial strategy to predict the failure of complex joint is very efficient in a modeling point of view. Indeed, the computational cost are reduced thanks to the multilevel strategy. However, the main drawback of this method lies in the identification of the parameters K_t and K_m which necessitates a huge experimental database. This is the reason why we propose in this paper a virtual testing strategy to identify this parameter (right of Figure 5).

Application of the virtual testing strategy to an industrial case

The present virtual testing strategy is applied in the section to an industrial test case presented in Figure 6. It is a generic bolted joint structures composed of three composite panels and light alloy buttstraps. The study is focused on panel 1 $[0/-45/0/45_2/0/-45_2/0/45/0_3/45/90/-45/0_2/45/0_2/-45/90]_s$, manufactured using T700/M21 unidirectional plies. The structure is subjected to a shear test in a double-frame device (see mesh and boundary conditions in Figure 6b).

Figure 6 : Picture of the composite junction subjected to a double-frame shear test (a) FE mesh and detail of the structure (b).

The identification of parameters K_t and K_m has necessitate to perform FE calculation, using the model presented in the first section, for (i) open-hole test, (ii) bearing tests and (iii) plane plate specimen with the nominal lay-up disoriented with an angle varying form 0° to 90° . Fifteen virtual tests have been necessary to identify these parameters. Finally, this analysis permit to perdict a failure load equal to 1390kN to be compared with the experimental load equal to 1260kN. The error is lower than 10%.

CONCLUSION

This study was aimed at proposing tools to increase the complexity and decrease the calculation cost for strength prediction of bolted junctions. This approach is based on a classical industrial multilevel strategy. A global calculation is first performed in order to evaluate the behaviour of the whole junction in its environment. The strength of the critical fixations is, in a second time, evaluated at local-level calculations. This local analysis is based on a simple semi-empirical model industrially identified on a huge experimental data basis. In order to reduce this experimental cost, a virtual testing approach is proposed. The virtual tests use a detailed simulation, physically based but very time consuming. This fine model permits reproduce the experimental results for various loading (open-hole and filled-hole in tension, joints subjected to combined by-bass and bearing load). It has been shown that such a virtual testing strategy has permit predict to failure load of a complex bolted joint structure.

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